

Crystallisation of six compounds with ALK2 complexed with FKBP12.

FKBP12 Purification

- Thaw pellets in luke warm water
- Sonicate all other samples for 5 min (5 on, 10 off) on ice.
- Divide each sample into two centrifugation tubes and top up with 'binding buffer' (500mM NaCl, 50mM HEPES, 5mM Imidazole, 5% glycerol, pH7.5) so each tube is full (approx. 40ml per tube).
- Add 1ml PEI (5%) per tube to precipitate DNA.
- Spin at 21.5k rpm for 50 minutes.
- Incubate each half of lysate with 2ml pre-equilibrated Ni-NTA beads at 4C for 1h. (500mM NaCl, 50mM HEPES, 5mM Imidazole, 5% glycerol, pH7.5)
- Spin down beads at 700g for 10 minutes to separate beads from lysate.
- Pour off lysate.
- Resuspend beads in 50ml binding buffer and load onto gravity flow column (collect flow through)
- Wash with 30ml wash buffer (500mM NaCl, 50mM HEPES, 30mM Imidazole, 5% glycerol, pH7.5).
- Elute in 7ml elution buffer 1 (500mM NaCl, 50mM HEPES, 50mM Imidazole, 5% glycerol, pH7.5).
- Elute in 3 x 7ml elution buffer 4 (500mM NaCl, 50mM HEPES, 250mM Imidazole, 5% glycerol, pH7.5).
- Run samples on an SDS PAGE gel (mix 5ul of loading dye with 15ul sample, boil for 3 minutes and load 10ul onto the gel.) and run at 160V for 50 minutes.
- Add Tev to relevant fractions (shown in boxes) and leave overnight at 4°C
- Combine and concentrate down fractions to <5ml
- Run on a GF75 size exclusion column to separate out FKBP12 from GST tag dimers.

FKBP12 purification: Top left – Nickel column fractions. Bottom left – GF75 fractions. Right – gel filtration trace from AKTA

Complex purification

BMPR1B and BMPR1A (previously purified and stored at -80°C were mixed with 5x excess of FKBP12 (fresh), concentrated down to <5ml, and the complex purified by size exclusion chromatography run in 50mM HEPES, 300mM NaCl, 1mM TCEP pH7.5 at 1 ml/min.

Top – SDS PAGE gel filtration fractions of the complexes of BMPR1A with FKBP12 and corresponding AKTA trace. Bottom - SDS PAGE gel filtration fractions of the complexes of BMPR1B with FKBP12 and corresponding AKTA trace. The red box indicates the fractions taken for crystallisation trials.

Complex was concentrated down to 13.3mg/ml and 7.5mg/ml respectively using a 3 kDa MWCO spin concentrator. Compounds from M4K Pharma were added to complex at a concentration of 0.7mM, the samples spun at 13,000rpm for 20 minutes and plates set up using standard coarse screens. 150nl drops were set up at ratio's of 1:2, 1:1 and 2:1. HCS3 and HIN3 plates were stored at 4°C while all other plates were stored at 20°C.

	M4K2009	M4K3003	M4K3007
BMPR1A + FKBP12	HCS3/HIN3/BCS/JCSG7	HCS3/HIN3/BCS/JCSG7	HCS3/HIN3/BCS/JCSG7
BMPR1B + FKBP12	HCS3/HIN3/BCS		HCS3/HIN3/BCS/JCSG7

Summary table of coarse screens set up for each compound and complex.

Plates were monitored at regular intervals until crystals were identified and mounted. BMPR1B complex crystals were spotted after 7 days. ACVR1 complex crystals were spotted after 28 days.

Crystal mounting

All crystals were grown and mounted at 4°C before being flash frozen in liquid nitrogen.

25% Ethylene glycol was used as a cryoprotectant, mixed with mother liquor from the well and added to the drop before mounting.

The following crystals were mounted:

BMPR1B-c017 + FKBP12 (XX03BMPR1B-p001) Compound M4K2009

Plate	screen	well	pin ID	Puck position	xtal no.
CI072473	HCS3	B6a	SS150E0101	Pos4	x001
CI072473	HCS3	B6a	SS150E0020	Pos3	x002
CI072473	HCS3	B3a	SS150E0072	Pos2	x003
CI072473	HCS3	G8d	SS200F0013	Pos5	x004
CI072472	HIN3	F6a	SS075C0198	Pos12	x005
CI072472	HIN3	F6c	SS075C0206	Pos1	x006
CI072472	HIN3	F8c	SS075C0185	Pos13	x007

ACVR1Z-c082 + FKBP12 (XX06ACVR1Z-p001) Compound M4K3003

CI071294	HIN3	G5c	SS050B0051	Pos10	x001
CI071294	HIN3	G5d	SS050B0024	Pos11	x002

HCS3 B6a M4K2009 BMPR1B + FKBP12	HCS3 B3a M4K2009 BMPR1B + FKBP12	HCS3 G8d M4K2009 BMPR1B + FKBP12
HIN3 F6a M4K2009 BMPR1B + FKBP12	HIN3 F6c M4K2009 BMPR1B + FKBP12	HIN3 F8c M4K2009 BMPR1B + FKBP12
HIN3 G5c M4K3003 ACVR1 (R206H) + FKBP12	HIN3 G5d M4K3003 ACVR1 (R206H) + FKBP12	

Crystals considered suitable for mounting.